

The Problem of Freedom in a Comparative Analysis of Eastern-Western Philosophy

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Received: Feb 10, 2026

Accepted: Mar 10, 2026

Published: Mar 23, 2026

Summary

The presented article analyzes the problem of Freedom, one of the main problems of Eastern and Western philosophy. The author, emphasizing that the approaches to understanding and analyzing a problem that actually has the same content and essence are very different and diverse, conducts research in this direction and comes to scientific-objective conclusions.

One of the conclusions of the author is that while Eastern philosophy emphasizes the interrelationship of phenomena and the limitations of human consciousness in relation to the world, Western philosophy tends to be analytical. Since Western philosophy emphasizes the role of reason and cognitive evidence.

The researcher, using materials on ancient Chinese, ancient Indian, Azerbaijani and modern European philosophy, identified the characteristic features of freedom in Eastern and Western philosophy, and also tried to clarify the comparative analysis of the attitude of representatives of both philosophies to the problem of freedom. The results of the study are of practical importance and can be used in teaching courses on the history of philosophy, social philosophy, ethics and multiculturalism. The concept of freedom has a social and practical orientation and can significantly help young people determine value priorities in the context of social interactions.

Keywords: East, West, personality, freedom, will, values, necessity, dialogue

Introduction

The study of the main stages and peculiarities of the evolution of the attitude to freedom in the history of philosophical thought of the West and the East is of exceptional importance in terms of a comprehensive and deep understanding of the theoretical and conceptual foundations of the formulation of this problem in modern social philosophy.

The relevance of the above-mentioned section should also be explained by the need to implement a dialogue between Eastern and Western cultures, scientific and moral values, under the influence of globalization trends. It is clear from the above that revealing the specific and common aspects in terms of understanding freedom in the way of thinking and theoretical thought of the East and the West is now more relevant than ever. In recent times, certain successful attempts have been made in this direction and it is important to continue them. Since freedom, by its very nature, has a universal content, it has been the focus of attention of both Eastern and Western thinkers in almost all periods. In this sense, the Russian philosopher G. Plekhanov (1856-1918) rightly noted that freedom stands before all philosophers and says to them: reveal my inner secrets, or I will eat and destroy your entire philosophical system [27, p.590].

1. Ideas of freedom in the East-West space

In the promotion and solution of all the main philosophical issues related to the concept of freedom (content, main directions, ways of achieving it, etc.), there have been and still are certain peculiarities determined by the historical conditions, scientific traditions, political, ethnic and cultural characteristics of the Western and Eastern regions, and they continue to be so. First of all, let us note that it is more appropriate to consider the concepts of East and West in terms of a whole region characterized by civilization, historical and cultural characteristics rather than in a geographical sense. The features that are characteristic of Eastern culture and lifestyle also find their corresponding expression in relation to the idea of freedom. These are the weakness of the reproduction of existing social forms, the strong stability in the lifestyle, the predominance of religious-mythological concepts, the regulation of the way of thinking, the disregard for the individual characteristics of the personality, the dissolution and disappearance of its interests in a kind of collective, etc. As a whole, the East is characterized by traditionalism arising from the cyclical nature of agrarian production, which is the main type of occupation here, the slowness of innovation tendencies to find their place, and the high role of the state (Eastern despotism). Due to these qualities, in the philosophy and general culture of that region, issues of moral education and social ethics were given a primary place in the behavior and actions of people.

Accordingly, the concept of freedom was also directed more towards family relations than towards public life in general (especially in the early periods). For example, in the teachings of Confucius (551 BC-479 BC), who gained special fame in Ancient China, special emphasis was placed on didactics and social ethics [13, p.51].

In general, in Eastern philosophical thought, private property was not given much importance, the main focus was on the issues of the spiritual life of the individual. For example, ancient Indian Buddhism declared the liberation of man from the law of karma to be the goal of his life. The community strictly controlled the organic coordination of each person's personal sensual desires with moral requirements and rules aimed at liberation from samsara. It was believed that only in this way could an individual be free from severe tortures and suffering in the world of samsara (punishment for one's actions in the afterlife) [14, p.186].

The strong role of Islam, which strictly regulates the life of the religious part of the population in the East, also hindered the development of the issue of freedom of conscience here. Then, the peoples of Eastern countries focused their main attention on the issues of organizing everyday living conditions, not devoting much space to other general and theoretical issues. Therefore, science in the East developed slowly. Here, innovations aimed at disrupting the stability of society were usually treated with jealousy. In the East, unlike in the West, knowledge that corresponded to corporate ethics and the interests of the state was applied. In the West, the interests of the owner-citizen played the role of a driving force in the development of new scientific knowledge. On the other hand, democracy, which is an important guarantor of freedom, was developing more rapidly in the West. This gave a priority to elected and representative bodies, unlike the monarchy, which exercises power concentrated in the hands of one person. True, democracy subordinated the will of a separate person and a minority to general interests, and therefore limited freedom within a certain framework. At the same time, it should not be forgotten that legal norms expressing democracy help to ensure freedom in a person's personal life. In this regard, as an important positive aspect of the West in relation to freedom, the activity of a perfect system of legal norms that protects the autonomy of the individual and his freedom from possible attacks by the state should be specially noted. On the other hand, the existing state structure here tried to implement equality and freedom in the personal lives of people.

In the East, as a rule, the individual, personal aspect of freedom, general aspects related to human dignity were discussed more widely. This can also be seen in the work of Azerbaijani thinkers who lived in the Middle Ages. The great Azerbaijani poet (N. Ganjavi 1141-1209) widely promoted the issues of human freedom and dignity in his works. In his work "Iskendername" he evaluated intelligence as the source of human morality, and freedom as a high blessing that allows a person to dominate nature [3, p.237].

1.1 The relationship between the rational and emotional sides in the understanding of the idea of freedom in the East and the West

Another aspect that manifests itself in the understanding of the idea of freedom in the East and the West is related to the explanation of the relationship between the rational and emotional sides. In this regard, it should be noted that in Western philosophical thought, freedom is more associated with the rational level. For example, Spinoza (1632-1677) showed that if a person gives preference to passions in his activity, he is a slave, but if he takes cognition as the basis, then he is free [32, p. 93]. In fact, both sides are closely related in freedom. In this sense, the Russian philosopher V.S. Solovyov (1853-1900) rightly noted that if a person had only intelligence, then he would want the best, his activity would be measured by a high level of knowledge. However, a person also has a passionate heart, therefore, precisely in order to satisfy his passions, the desire of his heart, he prefers the less profitable to the more profitable, and it is at this point that his freedom appears. In this regard, he shows, citing Aristotle, that since free will determines the quality of human existence, it should not be evaluated as a superiority of man, but as an immaturity of his nature [33, p. 449].

As in the West, thinkers in the East have put forward a number of valuable considerations regarding the relationship between free will and causality in the understanding of freedom. In this regard, the following opinion of the great Azerbaijani thinker M. Fizuli (1494-1556) is typical: "The people of the world are of two types: the first ones said that we have no authority in affairs... because the matter of our body from the beginning to the present... has been circulating independently of us and our will. It is the same now: we have neither freedom nor intervention. Therefore, they have surrendered to fate in their affairs. These are the people of surrender. The others said that we have freedom and will in affairs, if it were not so, we would not deserve reward or punishment, poverty or wealth. These are the causers. Most people are supporters of this belief, and this belief is true" [2, p. 100].

Another common feature between the West and the East in relation to the idea of freedom was also evident. It is the idea that carnal desires create an obstacle to true freedom. For example, the ancient philosopher Plotinus (205-270), one of the founders of Neoplatonism, noted that those people should be considered free who, being free from carnal passions, are governed only by their reason [26, p. 267]. This idea was later expressed in the work of the Azerbaijani philosopher Sh. Suhrawardi (1155-1191). He wrote in his work "Hikmatul Israq" that when I am free from my body, I observe the sacred field of light [44, p. 171]. Thus, like Plato (428-327 BC) and Plotinus, Sh. Suhrawardi also saw true freedom in being free from corporeality, material life, and attaining divine light. In the East, in the philosophical ideas of the early periods, the idea of freedom was characterized more as the destiny of the wise, as the spiritual ideal of the individual. This was not accidental, but arose from the nature of the social structure and historical conditions in those periods. Like the ancient philosophers, some thinkers of the East also thought that being free by realizing the necessity was not a quality that was accessible to everyone. On the other hand, since it was extremely difficult to fight for freedom against the violence of the state in a slave society, especially in feudalism, many thinkers saw the way out in enriching the inner world of a person. During the feudal period, the influence of Christianity in the West and Islam in the East (of course, in different ways) on people's ideas about freedom in this direction was even

stronger. It is no coincidence that in the past, freedom, as a rule, had an individual character and was limited to spiritual freedom, but in the new period, especially in the philosophy of enlightenment, it was supplemented with more socio-political and legal content. The mentioned tendency was also observed in the philosophy of Azerbaijani enlighteners. N.Cerulla gizi, who studied the views of Azerbaijani enlighteners on personality, writes that one of the main principles here is the issue of personal freedom [5, p.130].

Some of the enlighteners gave a general meaning to freedom. For example, the Azerbaijani materialist philosopher M.F.Akhundov (1812-1878) did not limit freedom to the boundaries of a single individual, but attributed it to society as a whole, writing: “Our goal is to raise the banner of freedom and justice high and give the people the opportunity to build their lives peacefully, to follow the path of prosperity and to get rich” [1, p.281].

Of particular interest is the analysis of the evolution of the idea of freedom in the history of philosophical thought by the German-born American philosopher E. Fromm (1900-1980). In his opinion, the religious explanation of freedom, the fatalistic description, and the presentation of freedom as a subjective feeling and understanding of one's own freedom are unconvincing. The first is aimed at strengthening faith in a divine power in man. The second expresses the desire to hold a person responsible for his actions and punish him. The third argument is unconvincing because many prominent thinkers (Spinoza, Leibniz, and others) have denied this position, showing it to be contradictory. Fromm also noted with regret that those who dealt with this problem after those philosophers did not understand that it was impossible to solve it without clarifying the issue of the determination of human activity by forces that we do not understand [38, p.89-90]. True freedom manifests itself when a person is not limited to giving preference to the first side in the relationship between rationality and feeling, but also takes care of the development of his feelings. In this case, it is very important to direct passions and feelings in a normal direction.

In Western and Eastern philosophical thought, the following aspect also occupies a wide place in the explanation of freedom. This is a matter of restraining a person's own feelings and self, and properly educating his sensual desires. It was first put forward in ancient Eastern philosophy, and later became widespread among European philosophers. For example, B. Spinoza, known as the author of a number of interesting ideas about freedom, notes that the main goal and ethical duty of a person is to achieve freedom, which is connected with his self-awareness. However, when a person becomes a slave to his feelings and passions, he cannot reach this level and, therefore, cannot act in accordance with his human interests and essence [32, p.104].

In Eastern philosophical thought, since ancient times, the idea that a person's ability to control his feelings, the power to control his soul, is the main way to educate him and rise to the peak of spiritual perfection has been dominant. Later, this idea became more widespread in the East, and even spread to Western philosophy, not limited to its borders. Thus, the idea in question was at the center of attention in Ancient Greek philosophy, as well as in Western philosophical teachings of the Middle Ages and the modern era. These teachings show that in order to educate the desires related to the soul and be able to own it, a person must expand his cognitive capabilities and raise the level of understanding. In this regard, the following idea of the great Azerbaijani philosopher Nasir al-Din Tusi (1201-1274) attracts attention: “The soul is such a thing that if you leave it to itself, it tends to debasement and sinks into the swamp, but if you restrain it and give it direction, it conquers the heights of virtue and reaches perfection [4, p.53]. The question of the relationship between the soul and freedom of man was posed in a slightly different way in the West. Here, this concept was often taken as feelings and desires. For example, Spinoza, who spoke extensively about the relationship between freedom and necessity in his work, also meant the natural physical feelings and instincts of man when he said determinism. In his opinion, when feelings and passions

subordinate a person to themselves, they do not allow him to act in accordance with his true interests and true essence [34, p. 104].

2. Attitude to the problem of freedom in the Eastern-Western philosophical worldview

The idea of freedom played a leading role in the Western philosophical thought of the New Age. This can be seen from the ideas of thinkers of that period about freedom. The German thinker I. Fichte (1762-1814) notes that his philosophical system is an analysis of the concept of freedom from beginning to end [15, p. 3]. The same attitude is observed in the philosophy of I. Kant. The Soviet philosopher S.S. Alekseev noted that all his creativity consists in answering questions about freedom, and for this purpose he wrote his three famous "criticisms" [11, p. 37].

The attitude to freedom of the prominent representative of German classical philosophy I. Kant (1724-1804) sounds quite relevant from the point of view of the modern era. In particular, his understanding of laws in the form of morality is of great interest at the moment. In this regard, the Soviet philosopher T. Oyzerman (1914-2017) rightly notes that in Kant's teaching, the subordination of the will to the law is taken as its subordination to morality [25, p. 70]. In general, the rational meaning of freedom occupied a dominant place in Western philosophy. The views of representatives of classical German philosophy on freedom are clear evidence of this. The famous representative of this philosophy, G.V.F. Hegel (11779-1831), linking world history with freedom, showed that historical development means the progress of the consciousness of freedom, and we must understand this necessity [16, p. 29].

Hegel, linking freedom with the development of state forms, noted that progress in the understanding of necessity expresses the process of transition from a less free state form to a more free state form. According to Hegel, progress on the path to freedom is characterized by the "democratization" of the state [16, p. 422]. Paying special attention to this point, the Soviet-Russian philosopher V. Asmus (1894-1975) notes that Hegel, unlike the ethicists of antiquity, as well as Spinoza, Fichte and Schelling, did not consider freedom to be the destiny of only the intellectual elite, but extended it to a wider mass of people [12, p. 16]. Therefore, Hegel's understanding of freedom differed significantly from that of the philosophers of antiquity and his immediate predecessors. Thinkers before Hegel considered freedom to be the destiny of only wise people, philosophers. In their opinion, it is precisely such people who can rise to the level of understanding necessity, that is, to the level of freedom. Hegel, on the example of Germany at that time, presented freedom as a quality that the people as a whole could achieve.

In general, Hegel's understanding of freedom attracts attention with the following three aspects: First of all, Hegel showed that freedom is not an eternal substance given to man by nature, but a social phenomenon that must be realized in the historical process. On the other hand, Hegel correctly revealed the relationship between these two concepts by explaining freedom as a perceived necessity. Finally, Hegel did not limit himself to treating freedom only as an internal, subjective phenomenon, but revealed and showed its close connection with reality.

On the whole, these or other ideas put forward in the West about the essence of freedom have not lost their relevance today. However, one cannot conclude from what has been said that the modern meaning of freedom is the same as it was in the philosophical thought of past eras. In fact, there are serious differences between them, and they are conditioned by the diversity of social life and the level of social cognition of the periods in question. At the same time, the progressive trends that took place in the development of philosophy itself played no small role in this regard. For example, the expansion and democratization of freedom, like

other philosophical ideas, can be shown. Thus, in ancient philosophy, freedom was attributed not to society as a whole, but to a group of people. The prominent thinkers of that time, Socrates and Plato, spoke only about the freedom of wise people [13, p. 164].

2.1 The role of the religious factor in understanding the evolution of the idea of freedom in the East-West context

When examining the evolution of the idea of freedom in the East-West context, it would be unfair not to mention the role of religion in this process. Because, religion had a significant impact on the formation of the idea of freedom in the corresponding periods in the history of philosophical thought of both regions. Even in the Middle Ages, the issue of free will was widely discussed in the teachings that emerged on the basis of the Islamic religion. The main dispute was between the oblivious and the predestined. The supporters of the first teaching claimed that free will does not exist, because when God created people, He determined all their good and evil deeds. As can be seen, they propagated fatalism and the idea of predestination. In contrast, the fatwaists showed that free will must be accepted, otherwise the idea arises that all human sins are determined by the divine itself, therefore they should not be responsible before God [6, p. 17].

It should be noted that in the West and the East there is no unambiguous approach to the issue of assessing the content and direction of the influence of religion on freedom. Thus, along with those who evaluate the positive role of religion in the development of freedom, there have been views that claim that religion occupies a conservative position in this process. It should also be noted that the second tendency is more characteristic of Western philosophical thought. For example, the English philosopher B. Russell (1872-1970) wrote in his work "Why I am not a Christian" that in the world it is necessary not to obey out of fear like a slave, but to struggle with understanding. He associated religion with ancient Eastern despotism and noted that all concepts about God emerged from ancient Eastern despotism. These concepts are completely useless for free people. In his opinion, for the creation of a good world, a dispassionate, cold view of the world and free understanding are necessary [29, p. 113].

When expressing an attitude to this idea, it should be noted that Russell generalizes the negative position and limitations of the Christian religion on the issue of freedom and considers it to be a characteristic of Eastern religions. In our opinion, this is a wrong position. In fact, behind the mystical side of the concepts of Islam and other Eastern religions about freedom, which is associated with attaining divine right, lies a deep belief in human freedom and the necessity of its attainment, which it would be unfair not to appreciate. The modern French philosopher, writer and playwright J. Sartre (1905-1980) also took a similar position, calling religion the enemy of freedom. Investigating his views on this matter, Russell wrote that Sartre takes freedom to the extreme. In his opinion, a person must choose his fate every time throughout his life. Whoever is afraid of this unpleasant truth seeks his salvation in a rationalized world. In this case, the scientist and the religious person are on the same level. Because both of them try to escape from reality and thereby make mistakes from the very beginning [31, p. 452].

At the same time, freedom is given a great place in Sartre's philosophy. He showed that the essence of human existence is measured by his freedom, and what we call freedom is inseparable from human existence [31, p. 90].

The Azerbaijani philosopher F. Ismayilov (1936-2018), who studied the philosophical teachings of J. Sartre, rightly pointed out that freedom is conceived here as absolute freedom of action and behavior. Freedom means that a person constantly creates something new in himself. A person who is equal to himself, that is, does not strive for something new, has no creative stimulus, therefore his freedom does not exist [7, pp. 150-151].

In the teachings explaining freedom from a religious perspective, its presentation as a choice between good and evil takes a central place. In general, the concept of freedom is one of the main ideas of the Islamic religious worldview. Islam requires that a person subordinate the animal desires of his heart to rational intelligence, which undoubtedly implies freedom. However, in the Holy Quran, freedom is not evaluated as a condition for action, but as an act. The act of freedom understood in this way implies a choice not between many alternatives, but only between two factors, namely between good and evil. Therefore, if a person uses the freedom given to him to harm himself and society, then Islam considers this an act of injustice and shows that the person who committed this is responsible before society and God.

Although the above idea is generally true, it should be borne in mind that when each person acts in a specific situation, the poles of good and evil do not appear before him in a pure form. In real life, a person is faced with many specific shades and options, therefore, he must take them all into account and consider them.

It should be noted that some Western thinkers interpret the issue of the attitude of the Islamic religion to freedom from a biased position. This is evidenced by the following opinion of the French Islamic scholar Dominique Surdel (1921-2014), professor at the Sorbonne University. He shows in his work "Islam" that the problem of fate (qadar) and free will in Islam is controversial. This issue also remains open in the hadiths of the Prophet Muhammad. According to Surdel, on the one hand, it is shown that man cannot do anything against the will of God, and on the other hand, it is stated that people will be questioned for their actions. Continuing his opinion, he writes that the Holy Quran does not show how to bring these two truths to a common denominator, how to reconcile them [35, p. 47].

When evaluating this position of Surdel, it is necessary to emphasize the fact that there were indeed certain disputes around the issue in question in Islamic history. For example, Al-Ash'ari (873-936), defending the position of the Mu'tazilites, connected everything with divine power and thus did not attach special importance to freedom. In contrast, the Islamic scholar Al-Maturidi al-Hanafi (852-944) and his followers considered human freedom unlimited.

From what has been said, it is clear that this problem, due to its complex nature, has not been unambiguously resolved in the religious teachings of different periods. However, this does not give Western thinkers a reason to take an unfair position against Islam and the Holy Quran. This can be seen from the fact that in a number of verses of the Holy Quran, the idea of being punished for one's own sins is emphasized. This means that a person is not only the executor of the will of others. From this idea, albeit indirectly, his free choice is emphasized. For example, the following ideas are expressed in three different verses of the Holy Book: "Man will only get what he has earned" [10, 53:39], "Whatever misfortune befalls you, it is the result of your own hands" [10, 42:30], "Search within yourselves the cause of your evil deeds" [10, 36:19]. Corresponding member of ANAS, director of philosophical sciences, professor S.S. Khalilov, emphasizing that in the West, indifference to the Islamic religion and its attitude to freedom has taken the form of a tradition, rightly writes: "The tradition of creating a wrong idea about Islam, of denying it without deeply understanding it, is characteristic even for those who want to reveal the connection of Christianity with other religions" [8, p. 217].

However, it would not be right to deny the different attitude of religion towards the idea of freedom in the West and the East. Thus, since the process of separation of church and religion from the state was proceeding rapidly in the West, the latter had a weak influence on all spheres of society. In contrast, in the East, Islam was strong and had great influence in all spheres of social life. Here, in fact, religion was not separated from the state. Therefore, in the West, faith in religion was almost invisible in the realization of freedom, the main hope

was considered to be the improvement of the economic and social system, the development of the legal system. In the East, the religious view that saw freedom in belief in divine power was very strong, especially in the Middle Ages. On the one hand, such a situation is explained by the dominance of religion, on the other hand, it was conditioned by the low worldview and level of consciousness of the population, and the strong presence of ignorance. In this regard, the ideas of the prominent Azerbaijani enlightener philosopher M.F. Akhundov, who lived in the second half of the 19th century, attract attention. In his work "John Stuart Mill on Liberty", he quoted the aforementioned English thinker and wrote: "In the world of living beings, man is a species that constantly demands progress, and progress is impossible without freedom of thought. The result of progress is called civilization in our time." Then he continued his thought and stated that civilization is such a general word that encompasses many things, the order of the state and the nation. Progress occurs when the individuals of a society express their opinions and do what they want. If the words or actions of this or that individual are acceptable in the eyes of other individuals of society, then they also accept it and find benefit in it, if it is not acceptable, other people declare that he is incompetent. This method is called "criticism". When there is freedom of thought, the benefit of criticism will be that in the end, the truth will take its place from the clash of different ideas and opinions and progress will manifest itself in the world of culture. If society does not give its individuals freedom of thought and forces them to be content with what their ancestors and saints have decided, not to go beyond it and not to use their minds in cultural affairs, then individuals will become automatons who plow the land, gather crops and do every task without thinking or reflecting; or they will be like mill horses that go around in a certain circle every day and eat barley and straw at their own time, drink water and sleep, wake up again the next day and repeat the same yesterday's life until the end of their lives. These poor horses will not know about the endless blessings in the world. If they were not tied up, they would travel the world and see places that please the heart and benefit from the blessings here [1, p.334; 350].

In this work, M.F. Akhundov showed that the benefits that freedom of thought can bring to society are incomparably greater than some of the positive aspects in the words of the religious and legal authorities: "Let us assume that some of the words and rulings of these religious and legal authorities relate to the mood of humanity and are not disobedient to authority, but since coercion appears in their thoughts and they eliminate freedom of thought, it is necessary to reject such corresponding rulings. Because the benefits that will be obtained from their laws are like a drop in the ocean compared to the harm caused by the lack of freedom of thought" [1, p. 356].

As can be seen, the great thinker of the East was able to understand that freedom of thought and speech plays an exceptionally large role in society. In this matter, his close acquaintance with Western European science and culture undoubtedly helped him a lot. When analyzing the evolution of the idea of freedom in Eastern and Western thought, one should not forget the following point. The point is that in the East, the solution to the problems of the existing society is sought in the personal quality of the head of state. For example, in the works of N. Ganjavi, and even earlier, the creation of the image of a just king in artistic thought is a clear proof of this. It was imagined that a just and intelligent ruler would create equality and freedom in society. In contrast, in the Western world, such hopes were associated with the development of people themselves, the improvement of the political system, and the creation of a state form that would fulfill the wishes and desires of the people.

3. Understanding the legal and factual forms of freedom in the West

In the West, special attention was paid to the interpretation of its legal and factual types in the understanding of freedom. This issue occupied an important place in the work of the German philosopher G.W. Leibniz (1646-1716). In his opinion, legal freedom is generally of a formal nature, however, when a certain threat arises to the freedom of individuals, it plays an important role, since it helps to exercise the rights provided for by law. This is especially evident in countries with developed legal systems. Leibniz gave more space to factual freedom. In his opinion, this form of freedom implies the possession of the necessary means for the implementation of the will and a person's own body. The fact that no other people interfere with any individual does not mean his true freedom, because in this case freedom has a spontaneous nature. True freedom implies a thoroughly thought-out activity [22, p.74].

The ideas of Schopenhauer, a prominent representative of Western philosophical thought, on freedom are of interest. In general, this thinker, who put the will at the basis of everything, conceived freedom as the absence of any obstacles in front of a person. In his opinion, there are three different forms of freedom (physical, intellectual and moral) depending on the types of obstacles. According to Schopenhauer, the first, that is, physical freedom is characterized by the absence of any obstacles in front of a person. The freedom of the people, understood in this way, means being governed only on the basis of the laws they have accepted, because in this case the people fulfill their will. The next two forms of freedom are also necessary in his opinion. However, their meaning is much more difficult to understand and reveal [40, 5.44-45].

The tradition of characterizing freedom as a perceived necessity, widespread in the West, was further developed by the famous German philosopher of the 20th century K. Jaspers (1883-1969). In his opinion, the actual freedom of a person is closely related to his awareness of the possibility of freedom. On the other hand, he claimed that freedom is inseparable from the goal of a person. In general, according to K. Jaspers, the actual freedom of a person is characterized by how he perceives the world. This quality allows a person to eliminate possible dangers, to understand his own successes and failures, as a result, a person gains his "I" [42, p.75].

Thus, according to his position, the realization of the idea of freedom means the understanding and realization of the possibilities of freedom. Therefore, it is very difficult for a person who does not understand the idea of true freedom to actually gain it. It should also be noted that in Western philosophical thought, a wide place is given to discussing the main reasons that give rise to freedom. E. Fromm (1900-1980), who paid attention to this point, showed that the Protestant doctrine gave impetus to the spiritual freedom of people, while capitalism continued it in the psychological, social and political plan. The basis of this development was economic freedom. Individuals were given freedom in economic activity so that they could reach all the heights that they could achieve with their diligence, intelligence and courage [38, p. 96].

The Western model of the meaning of freedom is also characterized by the fact that special importance was attached to ensuring the coherence of individual interests with public interests. It was believed that individual freedoms and interests realized in this way serve social progress. It should also be noted that the idea that public interests and individual interests do not contradict each other is not a new issue in Western philosophy. This was already reflected in detail in the work of the English philosopher (1632-1704) J. Locke [23, p. 593].

There is no doubt that this idea is very progressive. So, when there is correspondence and harmony between the individual and society as a whole in terms of interests, people do not approach social norms as rules that limit their freedom. Assessing them correctly, they

consider social norms to be a system of rules necessary to regulate people's activities on rational grounds. The functioning of this system contributes to the stability of social relations.

Characterizing the innovations brought by the West in the development of freedom in recent centuries, E. Fromm writes that man has become more and more free from attachment to nature, his power has risen above the level that he could have dreamed of. The previous caste differences and religious differences have disappeared, people have become equal and have learned to know each other. The world has become more and more free from mystery. Man began to look at himself objectively, less and less caught up in illusions. Political freedoms have developed. In the new economic conditions that have arisen, the middle class has begun to struggle for political power: the gained power has created new opportunities for economic progress. The main directions of this path were the English and French revolutions, the struggle for independence in America. In short, capitalism not only freed man from traditional bonds, but also created wide opportunities for the growth of positive freedoms, activity, and the development of a critical and responsible personality [39, p.97].

In certain cases, the understanding of freedom in the East and the West manifested itself in two extreme forms. Thus, in the first region, the spiritual existence and freedom of man were absolutized. In contrast, in the West, the independence of material activity occupied the main place. It should be noted that both of these positions are one-sided and limited in nature. They cannot fully and completely reflect freedom separately. It should not be forgotten that man, on the one hand, is a spiritual being, and on the other hand, he is a body, a physical being. He lives and acts in a certain socio-political environment, in multilateral relations with other people. Here there are certain laws that affect human freedom, and without taking them into account it is impossible to understand the true essence of freedom. As can be seen, the main difference in the understanding of freedom in the East and the West is revealed in the relationship between its individual and social types. Thus, in the first region, preference is given to individual freedom, and in the second, to social freedom. This one-sidedness, accordingly, expresses the imperfection of their way of thinking and worldview. From the above-mentioned point of view, one cannot disagree with the following opinion of S. Khalilov. "The difficulty of creating a whole system based on a single project from Eastern people of different shapes, each of whom is rooted in one atmosphere, reduces the value of the Eastern man. But on the other hand, the fact that the Western man is a standard brick from the mold of a single idea (constitution, law, formal logic, etc.) is a shortcoming in the eyes of the East" [9, p. 171]. From what has been said, it is clear that the West and the East act as two different, unique and sometimes alternative models of a single universal process of self-realization. Paying attention to the mentioned point, researchers who compare the thinking of the East and the West sometimes exaggerate it too much. They imagine the matter as if real freedom consists only of internal freedom, while political (external) freedom is a product of abstract thinking, a mechanical concept unrelated to life [37, p.21]. In our opinion, it is not correct to oppose these two main types of freedom to each other, because they are closely related to each other. Individual freedom (personal freedom) is a very important factor and indicator of the spiritual and general development of a person. At the same time, political freedoms (public freedom) also play a very important role in society. The ability of individuals, taken on a societal scale, to exercise freedom in their thoughts and activities depends in many respects on their level. As in the understanding of many other issues, the uniqueness between these regions in the meaning and interpretation of freedom is also manifested in the following point. In the West, society as a whole, including the idea of freedom, is based more on a rational way of thinking, where people's feelings and desires are not taken into account to the extent necessary. In contrast, the Eastern way of life and thought is dominated by the emotional side, with rationality being limited.

In this regard, it should be noted that the general successes achieved by modern Western countries have been achieved thanks to rational thinking, and it would be unfair to deny it. In matters related to freedom, this finds its expression in the regulation of social relations, the application of an efficient and effective legal system, adherence to the principle of the rule of law, individual desires, and the increase in rational evaluative influence. All this (the connection of individual sensitivity with social necessity, the application of legal norms, uniform social standards, etc.) not only ensures general stability in society, but also protects the freedom of this or that person from possible external interference. At the same time, the assertion of a strict and definite connection of freedom with the normative legal system in the rationalist way of thinking is, in a certain sense, limited. It is no coincidence that recently a number of Western thinkers have also defended this idea. For example, the famous Swiss psychologist, author of a number of works on the philosophy of culture, the founder of depth psychology, K.G. Jung (1875-1961), showed that "the liberation of consciousness from the clutches of irrational and emotional characteristics in Western man was achieved at the cost of violating the integrity of the individual. Now, while we are more disciplined, organized and rational, we have become primitive beings with a slave psychology shaped by upbringing and culture" [41, p.25].

What has been said proves that it is not right to exaggerate the role of the West in posing and solving the problem of freedom. It is undeniable that shortcomings are also allowed here in this regard. For example, the predominance of technological, economic and legal rationalism in the West, the crises caused by industrial society and mass consumption, are accompanied by a significant weakening of faith in goodness and spiritual development, and inner freedom. Since market relations, private entrepreneurship and free competition are widespread, benevolence towards a person, pity for his moral suffering, honesty, pity and other qualities sometimes fade into the background. As a result, there is a danger of the disappearance of the common moral basis that unites society, egoism and individualism are taking hold. Emphasizing that not only rational, but also irrational and emotional sides play a very important role in freedom, K. Jaspers also took a similar position. In his opinion, thanks to the moral qualities of life, people understand each other and feel their freedom. Since freedom is located outside the rational sphere, it is impossible to give it a rational explanation. Therefore, we should be content with only noting certain of its manifestations [41, p.451].

is no doubt that the above idea is generally true. However, it is difficult to agree with the idea that freedom is completely outside the rational sphere. Thus, the scientific meaning of freedom includes the close interaction of rational, mental and intellectual sides with feelings, emotions and irrationalities. In the East, unlike the West, the spiritual and moral aspects of freedom have been brought to the fore in almost all periods. Since such a way of thinking and worldview has continued here for centuries, the struggles for political freedom have been weaker than in the West. As a result, the mechanisms for legal protection of human rights have not been sufficiently developed.

While the evolution of the idea of freedom in the East and the West has been more political, in the East the issue of the internal freedom of the subject has taken priority. The famous Indian writer R. Tagore (1861-1941) criticized the meaning of freedom in the West, showing that under this name, not spiritual freedom is understood, but freedom to conduct research, work and political freedom. No matter how important these latter are, they do not mean complete freedom. True freedom begins from within, with the freedom of the soul [18, p. 193].

Discussion

The head of the Tetley tea company, the English researcher of Indian origin, Ted Faulconer, agreed with this idea and noted that representatives of liberal thought, including the philosopher, sociologist and economist John Stuart Mill (1806-1873) and the German philosopher of Russian origin, Isaiah Berlin (1909-1997), gave a great impetus to the development of the theory of political freedoms. However, they did not write anything about “self-liberation” [37, p.20].

A comparative analysis of the attitude towards the idea of freedom in the two regions in question shows that while wealth, private property and a rational approach were the main criteria in the West, in the East the spiritual freedom of man stood out as an important goal. In this regard, the following opinion of Faulconer attracts attention: “In the West we have lost most of the criteria of value, except for money and things acquired by reason. In the East, liberation or inner freedom has always been the supreme goal, the inner essence of freedom. How poor and ordinary a person lives is of no importance here. Achieving freedom is more valuable to him than material wealth” [37, p.167].

In general, the author who made a comparative sociological analysis of the value systems of the East and the West came to the conclusion that in the former, qualities such as collective responsibility, humility, respect for elders, patriotism, respect for motherhood and authoritarianism take precedence.

In contrast, the value system of the West is based on individualism, money, efficiency, striving for superiority, aggressiveness, respect for youth, ensuring equal rights for women in society, etc. [31, p.11].

This difference also finds its corresponding expression in relation to freedom. It should be noted that the material and spiritual sides of a person are inseparable. In this sense, the process of satisfying his material needs, the organization of production and social relations, and the rules of coexistence require more rational principles. From this point of view, it would be unfair to deny the important role of rationality and intelligence in all aspects of social life, including the understanding of freedom. However, since the human essence is expressed more in his spiritual being, irrational moments, feelings, and emotional states occupy an exceptional place in his free life activity. In this sense, it should not be considered acceptable for society to restrict individual freedom and the activity of human emotional will at every step. On the other hand, if the potential advantages and possibilities of rationality are not properly assessed in the effective organization of social and individual forms of life, including freedom, this leads to undesirable consequences. From this it becomes clear that although human spiritual freedom and material physical freedom seem different at first glance, upon closer inspection they are in mutual influence and unity, complementing each other. In other words, in Eastern philosophical thought, the ability of a person to think about his inner world and fight against his ego, no matter how important it is, is not sufficient for complete freedom, because where there are no freedoms in public life, and where the behavior and actions of the individual are totally controlled by society, freedom cannot be adequate to its own concept. Similarly, the freedom provided at the level of law and justice (i.e. external freedom), which occupies a dominant place in the Western way of thinking, does not correspond to the true ideal of this concept. Therefore, freedom that finds its embodiment only in the existing legal system, and does not rely on moral relations and moral norms between people, is characterized by being boring and dull. Similarly, freedom that is based on the wandering of irrational qualities, the overflow of feelings and ignores rational moments cannot be considered normal for society.

This proves once again that the synthesis of moments expressing the characteristics that are manifested in Eastern and Western philosophical thought about the meaning of freedom

should be considered the only effective way in terms of the realization of the general ideal of freedom of humanity.

Conclusion

Thus, the analyses conducted in this research work lead to the following main conclusions: Since the 20th century, the idea of the formation of a single common history and unity of mankind has increasingly dominated consciousness. In such conditions, the idea of isolating and opposing Western and Eastern civilizations from each other does not justify itself. The need for mutual exchange of the advantages inherent in each of the countries and peoples living in these two regions is becoming increasingly clear. The interests of accelerating the process of forming a system of universal human values, in which the idea of freedom also occupies a very important place, insistently require the conduct of the aforementioned dialogue. The Soviet orientalist, academician N.I. Konrad (1891-1970) wrote in his book "West and East" that humanity does not exist in the abstract sense, its history is the history created jointly by all the peoples and countries of the world. This can be proven by an infinite number of facts in any field (20, p. 452).

This idea can be said about freedom, which is an important universal value. Tracing the evolution of this idea in Western and Eastern philosophical thought proves that in its theoretical interpretation, common and similar aspects tend to increase in both regions (of course, taking into account the specificities inherent in each). The dialogue of civilizations, which acts as a requirement of the modern era, also leads humanity towards a common unity in the socio-philosophical understanding of freedom.

Our analyses show that the evolution of the idea of freedom has not followed an equal and straight path of development in the socio-philosophical thought of these two regions. This can be seen from the fact that in different periods of history, sometimes the East, sometimes the West, played a leading role in the interpretation and theoretical solution of the problem in question. Therefore, in modern conditions, there is an urgent need to generalize and synthesize the achievements and positive historical experience achieved in the interpretation of freedom in the philosophical thought of these regions. This would have an accelerating effect on the process of formation of a single universal system of values, in which freedom in the true sense of the word would occupy one of the central places.

As a result, the convergence of humanity towards the common ideal of freedom would be accelerated. In this regard, it should be noted that the unique geopolitical situation of the independent Azerbaijani state, its rich historical and cultural traditions, and the centuries-old experience of the struggle for freedom determine its increasing role in the modern dialogue of the spiritual values of the East and the West.

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